

Relationship between Cognitive Function and the Upper Limb Function in Multiple Sclerotic Patients

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Abstract

Background: Cognitive impairment and upper limb impairment are common disabilities in multiple sclerosis patients.

Purposes: The purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between cognitive function and the affected upper limb function in patients with M.S. Thirty M.S patients were selected from Abdullatif Jameel hospital, Dr. Soliman Fakeeh hospital and East Jeddah hospital.

Materials and methods: All patients were assessed for functional performance by the Action research arm test and cognitive function by Montreal Cognitive Assessment.

Results: The findings showed a moderate relationship between MoCA and ARAT. In contrast, there was a non-significant correlation between MoCA and age, and duration of illness.

Conclusion: There is a relationship between cognitive function and affected upper limb function in MS patients.

Key Words: Multiple Sclerosis, Upper limb function, Cognitive function.

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Introduction

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a chronic progressive autoimmune disease that affects both white and gray matter of the central nervous system (CNS)(1). MS symptoms vary accordingly to the functional system involved including Sensorimotor impairments, incoordination, cognitive decline, and neuropsychiatric symptoms which significantly impact life satisfaction and community participation (2).

Motor and sensory dysfunction of the lower limbs in MS patients are often the first manifestations to appear so most studies focus on them (3). However, 66% of the MS population also have upper limb dysfunction (4) that affects some of the daily life activities and hinders full society participation (5,6).

Many studies reported cognitive impairment in MS as a frequent complication (7,8,9) but the prevalence can vary according to multiple factors as the sample studied and the applied cognitive Assessment tool (10).

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The cognitive impairments in MS can represent in form of memory deficits, reduced attention, and slowing of information processing that interferes with the quality of life, household activities, social interaction, as well as job retention (11,12).

Materials and Methods

Thirty (21 females and 9 males) MS patients at age of (33.30 ± 1.32) years, recruited from Abdullatif Jameel hospital, Dr. Soliman Fakeeh hospital where they were assessed and medically diagnosed with MS (remittent and relapse type) based on careful clinical assessment and radiological investigations including computed tomography (C.T. scan) and/or magnetic resonance imaging (M.R.I.) of the brain. All participants signed a written informed consent before participation. Age, sex, and duration of illness were recorded.

Participants underwent assessments that evaluated cognitive functions and upper limb motor function. The cognitive assessment included Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MOCA) and the function of the upper extremity was evaluated through the Action research arm test (ARAT).

The Montreal Cognitive Assessment MoCA was designed to assess cognitive performance in patients with mild cognitive impairments, Alzheimer’s disease, and another neurological diseases. It assesses multiple cognitive domains which include attention, concentration, executive functions, memory, language, visuospatial skills, abstraction, calculation, and orientation with a total score of 30 points (13).

The Action research arm test (ARAT) was designed to assess the upper limb functions in patients with stroke, brain injury, and multiple sclerosis. Moreover, it assesses the coordination, dexterity, and activity of daily living by observation. The ARAT is divided into four sub-tests which include grasp, grip, pinch, and gross arm movement. It consists of 19 items each item scored from 0 to 3. 0 represents an inability to complete the task and 3 to complete the task normally. The total score is calculated out of 57 possible points (14).

Statistical Analysis

The data were analyzed using statistical software SPSS version 21 (SPSS, Inc., Chicago, IL, USA) and Graph Pad software. Descriptive statistical analysis has been made for all

variables, and all data were expressed as mean ± SD. Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was used to determine the relationship between different variables in this study. The level of significance is P< 0.05.

Results

The baseline characteristics of the patients are shown in Table 1. Patients included 21 males and 9 female MS patients. The average age was 33.30 ± 1.32 years and the average duration of illness was 22.00 ± 3.29 months in, as shown in Table1.

Table (1): General characteristics of patients, data are presented as mean ± SD or number of patients.

Items	N=30 Mean ± SD
Age (years)	33.30 ± 1.32
Sex (female/male)	21(70 %)/9 (30%)
Duration of illness (Months)	22.00 ± 3.29

As shown in Table 2 the results showed a moderate correlation between Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MOCA) and the Action research arm test (ARAT) (r = 0.66 and p=0.035). Data were listed in table (2).

Table (2): Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MOCA) and Action research arm test (ARAT).

	Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MOCA)	
	r	p-value
Action research arm test (ARAT)	0.66	0.035*

* Significant at p < 0.05.

As shown in Table 3 the results revealed non-significant correlation between Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MOCA) and age and duration of illness (r = 0.38 and p=0.28) and (r = 0.38 and p=0.28) respectively. Data were listed in table (3).

Table (3): Correlation between Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MOCA), Age, and Duration illness.

	MOCA	
	R	p-value
Age	-0.36	0.29
Duration of illness	-0.21	0.57

* Significant at p < 0.05.

Discussion

Patients with multiple sclerosis suffered Physical impairments that affect their functional independence (15). However, physical problems are insufficient to explain some debilitating performance in daily life activities, especially those that require high cognitive functions (16).

The result of the present study revealed a moderate relationship between cognitive function and function of the affected upper limb evaluated by (MoCA) and (ARAT). This was similar to the work of Benedict et al, 2011 that investigated the relationship between cognitive and motor functions in patients with MS and stated that Processing speed and executive function tests significantly predicted variability in motor performance (17).

A very recent study to investigate the impact of the structural damage in patients with remitting relapse MS on their cognition and motor functions, supported the integration of both Motor and cognitive testing in clinical practice as the reduced executive functions contributed to impaired motor performance (18).

In the present study, we used the MoCA which allows for an evaluation of global cognitive performance. The MoCA is more sensitive than the mini-mental state examination MMSE in screening for cognitive deficits (19), and it has higher internal reliability (20). More importantly, the MOCA is superior to the MMSE as it is more accurate in the detection of long-term cognitive impairment including executive functioning, attention, recall, and visual construction (21, 22).

Also, the results of the present study revealed a non-significant correlation between the MoCA and age and duration of illness.

In contrast to our findings, the study by del Ser et al., 2005 found that age, polypharmacy, previous cognitive impairment, and hypotension during admission are risk factors for the progression of cognitive impairment (23).

And in contrast to the findings of the recent research that investigated the correlation between demographic characteristics and physical and cognitive functions in older multiple sclerosis patients and stated that Information processing speed and physical function are strongly correlated (24).

This opposition may be attributed to the middle-aged presentation of the recruited sample so, we furtherly recommend testing a more aged

MS population.

Conclusion

It was concluded that there is a relationship between cognitive function and affected upper limb function in MS patients. Therefore, it is important to emphasize the cognitive function in a rehabilitation program for patients with multiple sclerosis.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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REFERENCES

1. Kister, I. et al. Natural history of multiple sclerosis symptoms. *International journal of MS care* 15, 146–158, <https://doi.org/10.7224/1537-2073.2012-053> (2013).
2. Davide Cattaneo, Ilse Lamers, Rita Bertoni, Peter Feys, Johanna Jonsdottir Participation Restriction in People With Multiple Sclerosis: Prevalence and Correlations With Cognitive, Walking, Balance, and Upper Limb Impairments. *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*, Volume 98, Issue 7, 2017, pp. 1308-1315
3. Kubsik-Gidlewska AM, Klimkiewicz P, Klimkiewicz R, Janczewska K, Woldańska-Okońska M. Rehabilitation in multiple sclerosis. *Adv Clin Exp Med*. 2017 Jul;26(4):709-715. doi: 10.17219/acem/62329. PMID: 28691412.
4. Spooren, A. I., Timmermans, A. A. & Seelen, H. A. Motor training programs of arm and hand in patients with MS according to different levels of the ICF: a systematic review. *BMC neurology* 12, 49, <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2377-12-49> (2012).
5. Pierella C, Pellegrino L, Muller M, Inglese M, Solaro C, Coscia M, Casadio M. Upper Limb Sensory-Motor Control During Exposure to Different Mechanical Environments in Multiple Sclerosis Subjects With No Clinical Disability. *Front Neurobot*. 2022 Jul 11;16:920118. doi: 10.3389/fnbot.2022.920118. PMID: 35898562; PMCID: PMC9309790.
6. Bertoni R, Lamers I, Chen CC, Feys P, Cattaneo D. Unilateral and bilateral upper limb dysfunction at body functions, activity and participation levels in people with multiple sclerosis. *Mult Scler*. 2015

- Oct;21(12):1566-74. doi: 10.1155/2015/720856. Epub 2015 Mar 9. PMID: 25839039; PMCID: PMC4369906.
7. Sumowski JF, Benedict R, Enzinger C, Filippi M, Geurts JJ, Hamalainen P, Hulst H, Inglese M, Leavitt VM, Rocca MA, Rosti-Otajarvi EM, Rao S. Cognition in multiple sclerosis: State of the field and priorities for the future. *Neurology*. 2018 Feb 6;90(6):278-288. doi: 10.1212/WNL.0000000000004977. Epub 2018 Jan 17. PMID: 29343470; PMCID: PMC5818015.
8. Buzaid A, Dodge MP, Handmacher L, Kiltz PJ. Activities of daily living: evaluation and treatment in persons with multiple sclerosis. *Phys Med Rehabil Clin N Am*. 2013 Nov;24(4):629-38. doi: 10.1016/j.pmr.2013.06.008. PMID: 24314681.
9. Riccitelli, G.C., Pagani, E., Meani, A. et al. Cognitive impairment in benign multiple sclerosis: a multiparametric structural and functional MRI study. *J Neurol* 267, 3508–3517 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00415-020-10025-z>
10. Al-Falaki, T.A., Hamdan, F.B. & Sheahead, N.M. Assessment of cognitive functions in patients with multiple sclerosis. *Egypt J Neurol Psychiatry Neurosurg* 57, 127 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41983-021-00383-4>
11. Costa SL, Genova HM, DeLuca J, Chiaravalloti ND. Information processing speed in multiple sclerosis: Past, present, and future. *Mult Scler*. 2017 May;23(6):772-789. doi: 10.1177/1352458516645869. Epub 2016 May 9. PMID: 27207446.
12. Clemens L, Langdon D. How does cognition relate to employment in multiple sclerosis? A systematic review. *Mult Scler Relat Disord*. 2018 Nov;26:183-191. doi: 10.1016/j.msard.2018.09.018. Epub 2018 Sep 15. PMID: 30268039.
13. Julayanont, P., & Nasreddine, Z. S. (2017). Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA): Concept and Clinical Review. In A. J. Larner (Ed.), *Cognitive Screening Instruments: A Practical Approach* (pp. 139–195). Springer International Publishing.
14. Yozbatiran, N., Der-Yeghiaian, L., & Cramer, S. C. (2008). A standardized approach to performing the action research arm test. *Neurorehabil. Neural Repair.*, 22(1), 78-90.
15. Wajda DA, Sosnoff JJ. Cognitive-motor interference in multiple sclerosis: a systematic review of evidence, correlates, and consequences. *Biomed Res Int*. 2015;2015:720856. doi: 10.1155/2015/720856. Epub 2015 Mar 9. PMID: 25839039; PMCID: PMC4369906.
16. Amatya B, Khan F, Galea M. Rehabilitation for people with multiple sclerosis: an overview of Cochrane Reviews. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2019 Jan 14;1(1):CD012732. doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD012732.pub2. PMID: 30637728; PMCID: PMC6353175.
17. Benedict, R., Holtzer, R., Motl, R., Foley, F., Kaur, S., Hojnacki, D., & Weinstock-Guttman, B. (2011). Upper and Lower Extremity Motor Function and Cognitive Impairment in Multiple Sclerosis. *Journal of the International Neuropsychological Society*, 17(4), 643-653. doi:10.1017/S1355617711000403
18. Mistri, D., Cacciaguerra, L., Storelli, L. et al. The association between cognition and motor performance is beyond structural damage in relapsing–remitting multiple sclerosis. *J Neurol* 269, 4213–4221 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00415-022-11044-8>
19. Freitas S, Simões MR. Construct Validity of the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA). *Journal of the International Neuropsychological Society*. 2012;18:1–9.
20. Larner AJ. Screening utility of the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA): in place of - or as well as - the MMSE? *International psychogeriatrics*. 2011 Oct 3;:1–6.
21. Geubbels HJ, Nusselein BA, van Heugten CM, Valentijn SA, Rasquin SM. Can the Montreal Cognitive (2015). Assessment predict discharge destination in a stroke population in the hospital?. *J Stroke Cerebrovasc Dis.*; 24(5):1094-1099.
22. Julayanont, P., Phillips, N., Chertkow, H., and Nasreddine, Z.S. (2017).The Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA): Concept and Clinical Review. To appear in A.J. Larner (Ed.), *Cognitive Screening Instruments: A Practical Approach*. Springer-Verlag, pp. 111-152.
23. del Ser T, Barba R, Morin MM, et al. (2005) Evolution of cognitive impairment after stroke and risk factors for delayed progression. *Stroke*. 36(12):2670-2675.
24. Bollaert RE, Sandroff BM, Stine-Morrow E, Sutton BP, Motl RW (2019) The intersection of cognitive performance, physical function, aging, and multiple sclerosis: a cross-sectional comparative study. *Med Sci Sport Exer* 51:986–986. <https://doi.org/10.1249/01.mss.0000563456.84857.0d>

